

Phase Recognition in Small Incision Cataract Surgery Videos: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

Phase Recognition in Small Incision Cataract Surgery Videos

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

SICS-155

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Cataract is the leading cause of blindness worldwide, most affecting life in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), and the mainly used, most appropriate, and most cost-effective cataract surgical technique for LMICs is small incision cataract surgery (SICS). While algorithms have been developed for automated video analysis of surgical performance parameters for the cataract surgical technique predominantly used in high-income settings, so far there were no datasets nor algorithms for SICS available [1, 2, 3]. This MICCAI challenge introduces the first SICS video dataset and offers teams the opportunity to evaluate effectiveness of their phase recognition algorithms. The dataset of 155 patients was recruited at Sankara Eye Hospital in India.

Analysis of surgical phases is important because it allows for quantitative comparison between different surgeons, feedback on identified critical steps, and detection of discrepancies from surgical protocols and because it is the first step for automatic assessment of surgical quality (Sim-OSSCAR) [4]. Our contribution is the first public dataset for SICS holding surgical videos and phase annotations of 155 surgeries with 18 distinct phases.

Currently, there are other public cataract surgery phase datasets like Cataract-101 (n=101 videos) or the IEEE Cataracts (n=50 videos) but they only show phacoemulsification surgery which is distinct from SICS in the following ways: SICS involves a larger 6-8 mm incision (2-3 mm for phaco), allowing for easier maneuvering of tools. The surgical phases in SICS are distinct, with steps such as Nucleus Delivery, Nucleus Prolapse, and peritomy not performed in phacoemulsification, which instead includes Trenching, Nucleus Emulsification, and Irrigation/Aspiration [5]. MSICS also utilizes specialized tools such as the Vectis, Dialer, Conjunctival Scissors, Simcoe Cannula, Cautery, and Crescent Blade, which are not used in phaco; conversely, phacoemulsification surgery uses tools like Phaco Probe, Irrigation/Aspiration Probe, and Lens Injector [6]. Still there is some overlap between SICS and phacoemulsification and teams could consider using the mentioned datasets for transfer learning strategies.

Despite SICS widespread adoption in countries of the global south, no publicly available dataset exists for for this surgery, leaving a critical gap in cataract surgery research.

Competitors are expected to submit a algorithm for predicting surgical phases based on the video data we supply and a short paper describing their approach. Additional details can be found below.

1. Müller S, Jain M, Sachdeva B, Shah PN, Holz FG, Finger RP, et al. Artificial Intelligence in Cataract Surgery: A Systematic Review [Internet]. Vol. 13, Translational Vision Science & Technology. Association for Research in Vision and Ophthalmology (ARVO); 2024. p. 20. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1167/tvst.13.4.20>
2. Tabin G, Chen M, Espandar L. Cataract surgery for the developing world. *Curr Opin Ophthalmol*. 2008;19(1):55-9.
3. Sommer, A., Taylor, H. R., Ravilla, T. D., West, S., Lietman, T. M., Keenan, J. D., Chiang, M. F., Robin, A. L., Mills, R. P., Society, f. t. C. o. t. A. O. Challenges of Ophthalmic Care in the Developing World. *JAMA ophthalmology* 132, 640-644, doi:10.1001/jamaophthalmol.2014.84 (2014).
4. Dean, W. H., Murray, N. L., Buchan, J. C., Golnik, K., Kim, M. J., Burton, M. J. Ophthalmic Simulated Surgical Competency Assessment Rubric for manual small-incision cataract surgery. *J Cataract Refract Surg* 45, 1252-1257, doi:10.1016/j.jcrs.2019.04.010 (2019).
5. Martin Spencer. Phaco vs. small-incision. *Ophthalmology*, 113(2):353, 2006. 2, 3
6. Maria Grammatikopoulou, Evangello Flouty, Abdolrahim Kadkhodamohammadi, Gwenole Quellec, Andre Chow, Jean Nehme, Imanol Luengo, and Danail Stoyanov. Cadis: Cataract dataset for surgical rgb-image segmentation. *Medical Image Analysis*, 71:102053, 2021

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Temporal Action Segmentation, Cataract Surgery, Deep Learning, Phase Recognition

Year

2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

- First cataract dataset containing video recordings of Small-Incision Cataract Surgery (SICS) technique
- First public dataset in the most commonly performed cataract surgery technique in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs)
- Biggest public, manually annotated cataract extraction surgery dataset

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

Task:

- Recognize surgical phases through analysis of the video recordings of the surgery by an appropriate algorithm.

Application scenarios:

- Usage of the phase annotation for protocol deviation recognition
- Phase information is important for identification of complications and can be useful for instrument segmentation

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

The 12th OMIA Workshop

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

Half day

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

The challenge will be part of the OMIA workshop which will be planned for an entire day and presenting results will be a subpart of the workshop. The time will be needed to present the overall ranking results and the top algorithms with slides prepared by the authoring teams.

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

We expect 10 to 20 participating teams. This is the first challenge hosted by our research group; therefore, we have no historic data to use, but after careful review of other challenges presented in the last years similar to ours, we expect the above-mentioned number of participants.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

After conclusion of the challenge we plan to publish the results in paper in an academic journal.

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

Participating teams will submit their containerized algorithms to the challenge platform ahead of the event. At the conference itself, only a projector will be needed for the presentation of the competing solutions and respective results.

We plan to run inference with the submitted algorithms on rented hardware, therefore we impose the following limitations on computation: Inference (including feature extraction) should take less than 4 hours and use a maximum of 30GB of VRAM to run smoothly on a nvidia-tesla-a100.

TASK 1: Supervised phase recognition in small-incision cataract surgery.

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Cataract is the leading cause of blindness worldwide, most affecting life in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), and the mainly used, most appropriate, and most cost-effective cataract surgical technique for LMICs is small incision cataract surgery (SICS). While algorithms have been developed for automated video analysis of surgical performance parameters for the cataract surgical technique predominantly used in high-income settings, so far there were no datasets nor algorithms for SICS available [1, 2, 3]. This MICCAI challenge introduces the first SICS video dataset and offers teams the opportunity to evaluate effectiveness of their phase recognition algorithms. The dataset of 155 patients was recruited at Sankara Eye Hospital in India.

Analysis of surgical phases is important because it allows for quantitative comparison between different surgeons, feedback on identified critical steps, and detection of discrepancies from surgical protocols and because it is the first step for automatic assessment of surgical quality (Sim-OSSCAR) [4]. Our contribution is the first public dataset for SICS holding surgical videos and phase annotations of 155 surgeries with 18 distinct phases.

Currently, there are other public cataract surgery phase datasets like Cataract-101 (n=101 videos) or the IEEE Cataracts (n=50 videos) but they only show phacoemulsification surgery which is distinct from SICS in the following ways: SICS involves a larger 6-8 mm incision (2-3 mm for phaco), allowing for easier maneuvering of tools. The surgical phases in SICS are distinct, with steps such as Nucleus Delivery, Nucleus Prolapse, and peritomy not performed in phacoemulsification, which instead includes Trenching, Nucleus Emulsification, and Irrigation/Aspiration [5]. MSICS also utilizes specialized tools such as the Vectis, Dialer, Conjunctival Scissors, Simcoe Cannula, Cautery, and Crescent Blade, which are not used in phaco; conversely, phacoemulsification surgery uses tools like Phaco Probe, Irrigation/Aspiration Probe, and Lens Injector [6]. Still there is some overlap between SICS and phacoemulsification and teams could consider using the mentioned datasets for transfer learning strategies.

Despite SICS widespread adoption in countries of the global south, no publicly available dataset exists for for this surgery, leaving a critical gap in cataract surgery research.

Competitors are expected to submit a algorithm for predicting surgical phases based on the video data we supply and a short paper describing their approach. Additional details can be found below.

1. Müller S, Jain M, Sachdeva B, Shah PN, Holz FG, Finger RP, et al. Artificial Intelligence in Cataract Surgery: A Systematic Review [Internet]. Vol. 13, Translational Vision Science & Technology. Association for Research in Vision and Ophthalmology (ARVO); 2024. p. 20. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1167/tvst.13.4.20>
2. Tabin G, Chen M, Espandar L. Cataract surgery for the developing world. *Curr Opin Ophthalmol*.

2008;19(1):55-9.

3. Sommer, A., Taylor, H. R., Ravilla, T. D., West, S., Lietman, T. M., Keenan, J. D., Chiang, M. F., Robin, A. L., Mills, R. P., Society, f. t. C. o. t. A. O. Challenges of Ophthalmic Care in the Developing World. *JAMA ophthalmology* 132, 640-644, doi:10.1001/jamaophthalmol.2014.84 (2014).

4. Dean, W. H., Murray, N. L., Buchan, J. C., Golnik, K., Kim, M. J., Burton, M. J. Ophthalmic Simulated Surgical Competency Assessment Rubric for manual small-incision cataract surgery. *J Cataract Refract Surg* 45, 1252-1257, doi:10.1016/j.jcrs.2019.04.010 (2019).

5. Martin Spencer. Phaco vs. small-incision. *Ophthalmology*, 113(2):353, 2006. 2, 3

6. Maria Grammatikopoulou, Evangello Flouty, Abdolrahim Kadkhodamohammadi, Gwenole Quellec, Andre Chow, Jean Nehme, Imanol Luengo, and Danail Stoyanov. Cadis: Cataract dataset for surgical rgb-image segmentation. *Medical Image Analysis*, 71:102053, 2021

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Computer Vision, Ophthalmology, Phase Prediction, Action Segmentation, Video Analysis, Classification

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Bhuvan Sachdeva, Microsoft Research India

Kaushik Murali, Sankara Eye Hospital Bangalore

Simon Mueller, University Bonn, University Eye Clinic Bonn

Singri Niharika Prasad, Sankara Eye Hospital Bangalore

Thomas Schultz, University Bonn, Lamarr Institute for Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence

Yanwu Xu, South China University of Technology (Liaison OMIA Workshop)

Maximilian Wintergerst, University Eye Clinic Bonn, Augenzentrum Grischun Chur (PI)

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Simon Mueller

M.Sc., B.Med., PhD candidate

University Hospital Bonn | Dept. of Ophthalmology

Mail: s.mueller1995@gmail.com

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)

- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2025

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

Self-hosting of the challenge via CodaBench (<https://github.com/codalab/codabench?tab=readme-ov-file>),
Challenge data will be published on Zenodo.

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://medvisbonn.github.io/>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Publicly available data is allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The winner of the challenge will get an award of 500 Euro. Further, the top 3 participating teams will be a guaranteed part of a publication of the challenge results and insights.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.

- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

For publication we will consider the 3 best performing teams (according to test-set evaluations of their algorithms) and per team up-to 3 team members will be given the opportunity to be co-authors on a publication summarizing the results of the challenge. If there are other interesting or innovative approaches besides the top 3, we will consider including them in the publication.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Training and Validation data will be published and a private test set will be hold back for the final evaluation. The participating teams are expected to upload a final docker container on our privately hosted CodaBench Instance (url will be provided later), that can be used to evaluate their method on the test set.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

A validation data split will be provided for the teams to evaluate their algorithms on.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

01.04.2025: (Pre)-Registration opens for Task 1 and challenge website opens.

10.04.2025: Estimated release of training data.

01.06.2025: Estimated release of validation data.

01.07.2025: Opening of the submission system for algorithms

15.08.2025: Submission for algorithms closes.

22.08.2025: Final deadline for submission of an short-paper associated with the submitted algorithm.

31.08.2025: Contacting the authors of top-ranked algorithms to prepare slides for oral presentation at MICCAI.

01.09.2025 - 23.09.2025: Final ranking of the results on unseen testing data.

Announcement of results at Workshop/MICCAI.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

An ethics approval amendment was necessary for the publication of the data, this was provided by our collaborating hospital on the 24.12.2024 with the approval number SEH/BLR/EC/2024/114.

Number of the ethics approval: 1

Ethics Approval number: SEH/BLR/EC/2024/114

Institutional review board: Institutional Ethics Committee of Sankara Eye Hospital

Location: Bangalore, India

Date: 17.12.2024

Link to ethics amendment request: <https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1FRpym7S3NzcjLnRxsx8ZlewEUxKvWI511/edit?usp=sharing&ouid;=102236150212694225030&rtpof;=true&sd;=true>

Link to ethics approval decision:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/12d7Zq1WX4l43jUectfWY1CwqLQbChwKv/view?usp=sharing>

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Code of the evaluation software will be made available on GitHub. The software will be written in python and support a linux operating system.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

We encourage the participants to publish their code also on GitHub, but do not require this.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Funding: German Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development (BMZ), the Else Kröner-Fresenius-Stiftung and supported by the funding program Hospital Partnerships of the Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) (funding line "academic", contract number 81294577).

The Lamarr Institute for Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence will fund the compute costs resulting from validation of the challenge results.

Only the organizers and members of their team have access to the test labels.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Education, Training, Surgery, Research

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration

- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Classification, Prediction

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

In a real-life application the SICS videos would be acquired from patients requiring SICS due to symptomatic cataract with a decreasing visual acuity of the patients.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Video data was acquired from real patients that had to undergo SICS for cataract related visual acuity decrease and who consented to their anonymized data being used for research purposes.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Color video recordings of the operating microscope with a resolution of 960 x 540 pixels and a framerate of 15 FPS displaying small-incision cataract surgeries.

Surgery durations range from 5:01 to 21:58 minutes, and the average video length is 13:05 minutes.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

No additional context information will be given.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No additional context information will be given.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Data will originate from performed cataract surgeries on patients in a hospital setting for post-hoc analysis for teaching and quality purposes.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithm should target the prediction of surgical phases in the provided videos. For each frame in the recordings, 1 of the 18 phases of SICS should be assigned by the algorithm. When no phase can be recognized in a frame, a "background" phase can be assigned. A target frame rate of 15 frames per second (FPS) should be achieved (lower than in the original videos to speed-up processing).

Which information from the videos is used for this purpose is up to the participants. One possible way to predict phases could be the analysis of the appearance and movement of surgical instruments in the lens area of the SICS surgery.

- peritomy: Conjunctiva is dissected to expose the sclera.
- cautery: Diathermy is applied to coagulate episcleral vessels.
- scleral_groove: A partial-thickness groove is made in the sclera.
- incision: The groove is extended to form a sclero-corneal tunnel.
- tunnel: A lamellar corneoscleral tunnel is dissected.
- sideport: A small incision for instrument access.
- AB_injection_and_wash: Balanced solution is injected to clear debris.
- OVD_injection: Viscoelastic is injected to maintain chamber stability.
- capsulorrhexis: A circular capsular opening is created.
- main_incision_entry: The tunnel is entered with a keratome.
- hydroprocedure: Fluid is injected to mobilize the nucleus.
- nucleus_prolapse: The nucleus is tilted into the anterior chamber.
- nucleus_delivery: The nucleus is removed via the scleral tunnel.
- cortical_wash: Residual cortex is aspirated.
- OVD_IOL_insertion: The intraocular lens is implanted into the capsular bag.
- OVD_wash: Remaining viscoelastic is removed.
- stromal_hydration: Incisions are hydrated for self-sealing.
- conjunctival_cautery: Bleeding is controlled with diathermy.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Consistency,Specificity

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Data are acquired with state of the art ophthalmological microscopes in three different OT (but the same devices) and supporting equipment. In practice this means the following device(s):

Operating Microscope: Leica M220

Beam Splitter: Leica 70:30

Camera: CCD Camera - Single chip - FHD

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

After videos were acquired they were first collected, then an alphanumerical id was randomly assigned and quasi-identifiers in the video and its metadata removed or made unreadable.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Sankara Eye Hospital, Bangalore, India

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Operations were performed by fully trained ophthalmological surgeons that completed their resident programs.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

One case represents the recording of the SICS surgery of one eye of one patient. Additionally for each case the ground_truth is provided in tabular form listing the beginning and end of each surgical phase and a

frame-by-frame annotation of the currently visible phase in .txt format.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

(public) Training: 100

(public) Validation: 15

(hidden) Test: 40

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

Most public datasets used in the related phacoemulsification have a size between 30 and 100 surgery recordings (Cataract-101, IEEE CATARACTS, ...). Some private datasets, like BigCat have up to 208 videos. We aimed to raise a dataset with a similar size for SICS resulting in the 155 videos.

Because we achieve a dataset of sufficient size, it was possible to design bigger subsets with 40 patients for the hidden test set (for higher reliability) and 15 validation cases for the individual evaluation in the competing teams. Both numbers are high enough to guarantee that each set contains recordings with different lengths, a factor that is highly correlated with complexity in the given surgery. Maier-Hein et al. report that the median test set contains 25 videos, which we tried to surpass to achieve the above stated aims [1].

1. Maier-Hein, L., Eisenmann, M., Reinke, A. et al. Why rankings of biomedical image analysis competitions should be interpreted with care. Nat Commun 9, 5217 (2018).

<https://doi-org.mu.idm.oclc.org/10.1038/s41467-018-07619-7>

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

Patients are recruited from a population representative for the general public in India with a 50/50% split between male and female. Due to the age-relatedness of cataract disease the average age of the patients is above 50 years.

The class distribution of surgical phases in the videos remains the real-world distribution because any attempt to increase the frequency of classes would disturb the temporal coherency of each individual video and not temporal relations could be learned. Additionally, ophthalmological surgeries are highly protocolized and a similar occurrence of frames per phase (or the duration of the phase) is to be expected in new videos in a real world use-case.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

Final evaluation of the submitted algorithms of the contributors will be done on an unseen, unpublished test set holding 40 (25.8%) additional SICS videos.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Annotation was performed by three senior ophthalmologists. To safeguard annotation quality the first 10 videos were annotated by all annotators and an intergrader analysis was performed. Because a high agreement was observed between the annotators (Cohen's kappa von 0.96), the annotators split the remaining dataset between themselves and completed the annotation process.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Annotators were provided with a list of phases to annotate and a annotation excel table to be filled out. Training sessions were held to introduce the format and answer questions. The decision for a table format was done because the annotators do not have a technical background and a simple, easy to use tool was needed to make annotation process as smooth as possible. A format for annotations and comments was provided.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

3 ophthalmological surgeons with at least 5 years of experience independently annotated the dataset.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

No Aggregation.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The videos were anonymized by placing a box filter across the 30 uppermost pixels to remove information about operation room, date, time and place of the surgery. Further the resolution was decreased to remove details of the iris that could potentially enable iris or retina recognition attempts.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

After annotation a few cases were randomly selected and checked by another ophthalmologist at the hospital in Bonn to safeguard annotation quality. Additionally, we performed intergrader analysis with a Cohen's kappa of 0.96 in the first 10 acquired videos. This guarantee good quality of the annotations and avoid potential errors in the ground truth.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

Some of the videos have some pixelation artifacts due to compression in the video equipment.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

- Accuracy (frame-wise)
- Edit distance [also known as Levenshtein Distance] (phase-wise)
- F1-score (frame-wise)
- Precision-Recall area under curve (PR AUC)

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

Per-frame accuracy and F1-score are good metrics to get a general idea of the performance of the algorithm on a per-frame basis. F1-score is less sensitive to class imbalances and is added to avoid overestimations by the accuracy.

The edit distance describes (on a per-phase basis) how many manipulations of the found phase predictions have to be done to get the correct phases in the surgery ground truth, and is robust against class imbalances [1].

We added the PR AUC metric to also get a reliable score due to the varying frequency of the different classes. ROC AUC can be overly optimistic for multi-class predictions but has been included due to the fact that other publications in this area often report it.

1. Li S, Abu Farha Y, Liu Y, Cheng M-M, Gall J. MS-TCN++: Multi-Stage Temporal Convolutional Network for Action Segmentation 2020 June 01, 2020:[arXiv:2006.09220 p.]. Available from: <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2020arXiv200609220L>

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

All metrics are calculated for each case and averaged across all cases in the validation or test set. We will adopt a point-based ranking method supported by statistical analysis for robustness.

We choose the significance level $\alpha = 5\%$.

For each metric m_k , $k = 1, \dots, o$:

1. Determine performance m of each algorithm for each test case
2. Perform all pairwise comparisons between algorithms with the values using Wilcoxon signed rank test (with α)
3. Determine a significance score which equals the number of algorithms performing significantly worse than the current algorithm according to the test
4. Compute the ranking (shared ranks possible) based on the scores (1 to n) with the highest score corresponds to the best algorithm(s) (rank 1)

The final ranking over all metrics is computed by aggregating the significance scores over all metrics by the mean.

For a more formal description of this, we refer to the excellent best-practice guidelines in the supplement provided by Maier-Hein et al. [1].

1. Maier-Hein, L., Eisenmann, M., Reinke, A. et al. Why rankings of biomedical image analysis competitions should be interpreted with care. Nat Commun 9, 5217 (2018).

<https://doi-org.mu.idm.oclc.org/10.1038/s41467-018-07619-7>

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Missing data in the algorithm output is not allowed, for each frame a class prediction should be done, but it is possible to predict the background class for frames where the action is unclear.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

To rank the results from competing teams the proposed statistical analysis is to rank participants with the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test.

We decided for this ranking method based on the research published by Maier-Hain et al. who determined that metric-based ranking (aggregate, than rank) yields more robust results than case-based [1]. Our approach follows directly their proposed best practices for significance rating.

1. Maier-Hein, L., Eisenmann, M., Reinke, A. et al. Why rankings of biomedical image analysis competitions should be interpreted with care. Nat Commun 9, 5217 (2018).

<https://doi-org.mu.idm.oclc.org/10.1038/s41467-018-07619-7>

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

- Missing data is not accepted for phase predictions, unknown regions can be marked as "background"

- We provide a relatively big test set (n=40) and therefore variability analysis is not necessary.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

The Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test is used because it does not require an normal distribution of the metrics results per case and is therefore a good basis for our ranking.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

There is no further analysis applicable for this scenario.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

N/A

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A